

EARTH SCIENCES

DIGITAL MODELING OF GRAVITY-MAGNETIC ANOMALIES

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the issue of modeling gravitational and magnetic anomalies, which is very important in solving the main - geological problem of gravity and magnetic exploration. When solving complex geological and geophysical problems using modern digital methods of processing and interpretation, it is very important to correctly specify the physical and geological model of the geological object under study. In a particular case, a more accurate assessment of the gravitational effects of model geological structures is very important. For this, homogeneous bodies of regular shape are usually used, such as a ball, cylinder, prism, etc. In this case, a two-dimensional or three-dimensional geological structure is represented as a set of bodies of regular shape. An algorithm and Force-Fortran program Gteor have been developed at the Geophysics Department of the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, which allows calculating the gravitational and magnetic effects of magnetized two-dimensional bodies of arbitrary shape located at any depth. Using this algorithm, an assessment of the gravitational and magnetic influence of model geological bodies of arbitrary shape was performed.

Keywords: two-dimensional body, two-dimensional rectangular prism, model gravitational field, model magnetic field, digital modeling.

Introduction

In prospecting, exploration and study of the geological structure of promising oil and gas and ore-bearing areas, gravimetric and magnetic exploration methods are of great importance. They are based on the study of the nature of the distribution of gravitational and magnetic fields created by individual structural uplifts with excess density and magnetic susceptibility of the constituent rocks. At the stage of quantitative interpretation of gravimetric data, a very important task is solved - modeling of gravimetric anomalies, which is of great importance in the geological interpretation of gravimetric exploration data. At present, this problem is solved using modern graphic programs in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions based on the results of computer calculations of theoretical gravitational fields using developed algorithms and programs, which provides the most complete idea of the shape, depth and size of the desired geological objects [1-4,7]. This explains the relevance of scientific research conducted in this direction. The aim of the present research is digital modeling of local gravity-magnetic anomalies from model magnetized bodies and structures. As is known, in the conditions of Azerbaijan, volcanogenic-

sedimentary deposits of the Upper Cretaceous are widely distributed, which are well displayed in gravity-magnetic fields and are promising in terms of oil and gas [5,8].

Method and results.

For performing digital modeling, the Force-Fortran program Gteor, which was developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, was used. First, a two-dimensional model of arbitrary shape was compiled. The model has a shape similar to an anticline and lies at a depth of 4 km, with an amplitude of approximately 1.8 km. Then, the initial data were prepared for working with the Gteor program [5]. For this, a two-dimensional body of arbitrary shape was divided into elementary two-dimensional prisms with a certain step according to the Gteor algorithm. Then, the initial data were prepared for input into the computer. The figure below shows the results of this program (Fig.1). The top line contains the following initial data:

1. The number of elementary two-dimensional prisms of an arbitrary model ($N=6$), the initial and final coordinates of the points for calculating the vertical component of gravity V_z and magnetic

	N	X1	X2	EMAX	DX	SIG	J	
	6	-3.0	10.0	6.0		1.0	0.2	20
Z1		3.50	2.50	2.20	2.50	2.80		3.50
Z2		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00		4.00
	N	X	G	ZA				
	1.00	-3.00	1.44	-2.82				
	2.00	-2.00	1.90	-2.13				
	3.00	-1.00	2.52	-0.05				
	4.00	0.00	3.32	4.36				
	5.00	1.00	4.20	11.14				
	6.00	2.00	4.87	17.45				
	7.00	3.00	5.05	18.82				
	8.00	4.00	4.67	14.85				
	9.00	5.00	3.94	8.76				
	10.00	6.00	3.12	3.26				
	11.00	7.00	2.38	-0.34				
	12.00	8.00	1.81	-2.11				
	13.00	9.00	1.39	-2.72				
	14.00	10.00	1.08	-2.75				

Fig. 1. Results of the GTEOR program (calculation of the vertical component of the intensity of gravitational and magnetic fields)

field Za (X1=-3.0 km, X2= 10 km), the abscissa of the extreme point of the initial magnetized model (EMAX=6 km), the step of dividing the model into elementary prisms and the step of observation points (the step of the coordinates of the calculation points), which is 1 km, the excess density of the initial model and the magnetization intensity (SIG =0.2 g/cm³, J= 20 gamm).

2. Next, the values of the depths of the upper and lower edges of prisms Z1 and Z2 are printed. Below, the following values calculated by the Gteor program are printed separately in columns: N is the number of the observation point, X is the coordinate of the observation point along the profile, Vz are the values of the vertical component of gravity and ZA is the magnetic field intensity.

Based on the calculation results, the Vz and Za curves were plotted along the profile using the Excel program (Fig. 2). As can be seen, the compiled model in the form similar to an anticline is displayed in the gravity field as a maximum gravity with an amplitude of 5 mGal and a maximum magnetic field intensity of 18 gamm. Moreover, the magnetic field intensity curve intersects the OX axis at points 3 and 11 km, and is characterized by negative values with an intensity of 2.5 gamm at the edges.

Next, we performed digital modeling of the magnetic and gravity field of the Zardob-Muradkhanly area of the eastern part of the Middle Kura depression of Azerbaijan. As is known, the section of this area includes volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits of the Upper Cretaceous, which have magnetic properties [6,9]. The

Zardob uplift is located in the northwestern part of the Zardob-Muradkhanly anticline zone of the Muradkhanly oil and gas region. The Zardob structure was identified in the late 60s of the last century by seismic exploration using the reflected wave method. In the area, gravimetric and magnetometric works were carried out in the 70s to summarize the materials, and in the 80s, high-precision and area gravity-magnetic research works were carried out. These uplifts are well displayed in the gravitational and magnetic fields in the form of local gravity-magnetic anomalies. As is known, according to the Izotr program developed at the department, various transformations of gravity-magnetic fields were carried out, in particular in the Middle-Kur depression, where the Zardob-Muradkhanly uplifts are located [4]. Based on these transformations, various maps of local anomalies were manually constructed, including a map of local magnetic anomalies ΔZ_{10} , on which the Zardob and Muradkhanly uplifts are displayed as a single maximum of the vertical component of the magnetic field. As indicated above, we performed digital modeling of this magnetic maximum using the world-famous digital graphical program Surfer [10]. As a result, a map of local magnetic anomalies was constructed in the modern interface (Fig. 3). As can be seen in the figure, the intensity of this local maximum reaches 19 gamm. The local anomaly has an elongated shape oriented in the northwestern and southeastern directions (Fig. 3). In the northwestern part of this maximum, a relative maximum associated with the Zardob uplift is traced.

Fig. 2. Intensity curves of gravitational and magnetic fields from a model of a magnetized geological body

Conventional designations:
 A - two-dimensional model of a magnetized geological body; B - the curve of the vertical component of

the intensity of the magnetic field; C - the curve of the vertical component of the intensity of the gravitational field

Fig. 3. Local magnetic maximum of the magnetic field ΔZ_{10} in 2D version (Zardob-Muradkhanly area)

The observed single maximum is divided into two corresponding maxima of the magnetic field on the transforms of a smaller transformation radius. The spatial orientation of this single magnetic maximum is well displayed on the 3D map (Fig. 4). The joint composition of these maps provides a comprehensive and complete representation of the Zardob - Muradkhanly local maximum of the magnetic field (Fig. 5). The figures

below show the results of digital modeling of the gravity field of the Muradkhanly uplift in 2D and 3D variants and their joint composition, which provide a more complete spatial representation of the local gravity field of the Muradkhanly uplift (Fig. 6-8). As can be seen, the amplitude of the local maximum of the Muradkhanly uplift reaches 4.5 mGal, and the maximum itself has a slightly elongated shape, oriented in the north-west direction [3].

Fig. 4. Local magnetic maximum of the magnetic field ΔZ_{10} in 3D version (Zardob-Muradkhanly area)

Fig. 5. Composition of maps of local magnetic maximum ΔZ_{10} in 2D and 3D versions (Zardob-Muradkhanly area)

Fig. 6. Local maximum of gravity force Δg_{10} in 2D version (Muradkhanly area)

Fig. 7. Local maximum of gravity force Δg_{10} in 3D version (Muradkhanly area)

Fig. 8. Composition of maps of local gravity anomaly Δg_{10} in 2D and 3D versions (Muradkhanly area)

Conclusions:

1. A model of a two-dimensional geological body in the form of an anticline was constructed. To assess the gravitational and magnetic influence of this model of a two-dimensional body, the Force-Fortran program Gteor, developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, was used. To work with this program, the initial data were prepared in accordance with the algorithm of this program.

2. Calculations were made using the Gteor program for the intensity of gravitational and magnetic fields from a model of a magnetized geological body, on the basis of which curves of the vertical component of the magnetic field intensity and the vertical component of the gravitational field intensity were constructed using the Excel program.

3. Digital modeling of the local magnetic anomaly ΔZ_{10} of the magnetic field of the Zardob-Muradkhanly area was performed using the Surfer program. 2D and 3D maps of the local magnetic anomaly ΔZ_{10} of the magnetic field of the Zardob-Muradkhanly area were constructed, and a spatial composition of these maps was performed, which provides the most complete spatial representation of the magnetic field of the studied area. Comparison of the maps of the gravity field model and the local gravity anomaly confirms the Mesozoic nature of the local magnetic anomaly of the Zardob-Muradkhanly area.

4. Digital modeling of the map of the local gravity anomaly Δg_{10} of the gravitational field of the Muradkhanly area was performed, and a spatial composition of these 2D and 3D maps was performed, which provides the most complete spatial representation of the gravitational field of the studied area. Comparison of the maps of the gravity field model and the local gravity anomaly confirms the Mesozoic nature of the local gravity anomaly of the Muradkhanly area.

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